

THE NEED TO FURTHER POPULARIZE HAND COMBAT IN THE ARMED FORCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article reflects on the need to further popularize and study hand combat in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Moreover, continuing the historically rich values of hand-to-hand combat, proposals were made on the surface of issues of further popularization of it on the scale of the Armed Forces.

Keywords. Armed Forces, hand-to-hand combat, boxing, combat training, training process, physical fitness, soldier.

Collecting, studying the wealth of creativity created by the Uzbek people for thousands of years, passed down from generation to generation, educating the younger generation on the basis of these rich treasures as spiritually rich, morally pure, physically perfect is one of the pressing issues of today.

After all, “Our land has long been rich in poles and boaters, who are our judges and defenders, and care for them with kindness”[1].

In particular, methods and tactics in hand-to-hand combat showed their forms of manifestation not only in modern times, but also in history. This sport is one of the oldest sports of human activity and has been counted by military personnel in armies as important means of self-defense.

In addition to the excellence of global and interregional high-precision weapons of various levels in countries of the world and their unlimited destructive power, it does not exclude the possibility of the emergence of close combat sharites, which remain the final stage of organized armed confrontation. Currently, combat

operas conducted in different regions of the world show that the command of the armed forces of foreign armies still pays great attention to the preparation of physical training, in particular, hand-to-hand combat.

In foreign countries, today a number of scientific studies are being carried out to improve the functional, technical, tactical, psycho-emotional training of cadets (listeners) in the development of their combat training. For example, in the US and German armed forces, the mastery of hand-to-hand combat methods is carried out in combat training and is regulated by separate regulations and manuals, while great attention to physical training by the command of foreign troops, in particular, hand-to-hand combat, in turn, is explained by the fact that military personnel provide high physical and psychological training.

It is known to all that hand combat is among the sports that have long been popular in its content with the incorporation of methods and actions used in sports such as boxing, karate, wrestling, sambo.

The role of hand combat in combat and psychological training by foreign specialists in matters of hand combat as an object of research and aimed at developing and improving the basic physical qualities of military personnel, as well as forming motor skills and improving the technical actions necessary for solving tactical tasks during combat (S.V.Nikishev, P.I.Zaev, A.A.Nikolaev, I.A.Voronov, R.A.Gavrilenko, A.N.Kochergin, D.A.Kartamyshev) scientific research work.

If we look at the history of hand-to-hand combat, then first of all it has an ancient history, like humanity itself. According to historical sources that have survived, at the dawn of the development of civilization, people took up certain methods of attack and defense. In one of the ancient Egyptian pyramids, which has a history of several hundred years, scientists have found about 400 paintings featuring various methods of struggle[5].

Since that time, the acquisition of hand-to-hand combat methods has always been the center of attention in the training of professional soldiers of all armies of

the world, from which it has been widely used. Hand-to-hand combat has been a key element of military action until the advent of firearms in the world.

Speaking of “Oriental martial arts” in general, each country has its own martial arts. For example, national martial arts such as “u-shu” have been formed in China, “Taekwon-do” in Korea, “Vo-Dao” in Vietnam, “bu-jisu” in Japan.

In particular, our country also has a rich tradition of many solo martial arts. Among them, it should be noted that hand-to-hand combat in itself is distinguished by the fact that it concentrates sports such as boxing, taekwondo, wrestling, karate, sambo, u-shu.

It is from this point of view that one of the main reasons for introducing hand combat into the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the versatility of the training process in training; the need for unarmed resistance in an enemy armed with cold or firearms (in some cases, the use of an existing firearm poses a threat to infrastructure facilities or; it is manifested in the fact that it trains several characteristics, such as capturing an enemy or exiting enemy chokes, and having the necessary psycho-emotional ability and strong will in combat situations.

It is from this point of view that one of the main reasons for introducing hand combat into the system of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the versatility of the training process in training; the need to provide unarmed resistance (in some cases, the use of an existing firearm poses a threat to infrastructure facilities or people around them) in an enemy armed with a cold or firearm; physically energetic in relation to the employee or in conditions of fighting against several opponents at the same time; the need to overcome the enemy using demolition and painful methods; it is manifested in the fact that it trains several characteristics, such as capturing an enemy or exiting enemy chokes, and having the necessary psycho-emotional ability and strong will in combat situations.

It should be said that today, as a result of further popularization of hand-to-hand sports in our country among the population, especially young people, military personnel of the armed forces and employees of law enforcement agencies,

strengthening the material and technical base for the industry and increasing attention to the training of qualified personnel, trainers and judges, more than 10 thousand young people and. Due to the emphasis on hand fighting, 230 Uzbek masters of sports and 60 international masters of sports in this sport are growing[4].

The introduction of hand-to-hand combat to the annual “Army Games” Programme among Commonwealth of independent states countries, as well as the prizes won in recent years, is a factor in the growing interest of even more servicemen in the sport.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 In accordance with the decree of PF-5924 “On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan”[2] and the decision of PQ-287 “On measures to further develop the sport of hand-to-hand combat” of June 20, 2022[3], hand-to-hand combat as a priority sport is being phased into physical training of the armed forces and law enforcement agencies.

Today, in a taxidical time, in the possibility of facing a criminal from military personnel in close combat conditions, it is first of all necessary to protect oneself from him and have the skills to disarm and capture a criminal. This, in turn, requires high physical training from military personnel as well as excellent mastery of hand-to-hand combat techniques.

One of the important means of increasing the militancy of the personal composition of the armed forces, based on those in their country, is to establish a mutual continuity of moral and mental and physical training in the conditions of close combat.

In this regard, we think that in order to continue this sport not only in the Armed Forces, but also to prepare young people in every possible way for the future love of the motherland and its protection, it is necessary to pay attention to the following areas in order to continue the historically rich values of hand combat:

First of all, to constantly hold competitions in hand-to-hand combat and to establish the identification, selection and selection (selection) of talented athletes;

Secondly, the formation of the necessary material and technical base and infrastructure for engaging in hand-to-hand combat and the introduction of a system for training professional trainers, referees and specialists (instructors) in hand-to-hand combat;

Thirdly, the gradual introduction of hand combat as a priority sport into the physical training of the Armed Forces and law enforcement agencies and the development of educational and methodological manuals;

Fourth, widespread promotion among Armed Forces personnel and law enforcement officers and among the population, including through the media.

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